

Pakistan and Isreal; Friends Or Foes: An Analysis

by

Mahmoona Bashir, Sapna Razzak, Babar Hassan, Tabassam Fatima
Bahria University, Karachi

Abstract

Pakistan and Israel are considered as ideological twins. Because these both countries got freedom on the basis of their religions. But both never had any diplomatic relations with each other, neither both had any war directly. There are various reasons of not recognizing Israel as a state, one of the main reasons is solidarity with the Muslims of Palestine. Israel and Pakistan tried to establish ties with each other but somehow did not work. Israel's relation with India has completed it's 25 years and it has some major impact on Pakistan. Moreover, another reason for not recognizing Israel is that we the Muslims believe that Islam restrains us to do so. Nonetheless if relationship between Pakistan and Israel is established, Pakistan can benefit from Israel in many ways. This research paper will answer if it is possible for Pakistan to recognize Israel? What are the main reasons for not recognizing Israel? Lastly, can Pakistan and Israel be friend?

Keywords: Pakistan- Israel relations, Israel's relations with Middle East, Israel friend or foe.

Pre-Creation Scenario of Pakistan and Israel:

Before Partition both India and Pakistan were under the rule of Britain. Quaid-e- Azzam Muhammad Ali Jinnah worked hard for the creation of Pakistan. Dr. Allam Muhammad Iqbal had a deep inspiration of the Muslims of sub-continent. He infused a moving spirit and identity in Muslims of India. By the efforts of Quaid-e- Azzam the Muslim league held its annual session on 22-24 March 1940. The Lahore Resolution was passed on March 23rd, 1940. The British Government passed the Indian Independence Act on July 15th 1947. Due to the efforts made by Quaid-e- Azzam British government was compelled to divide Sub-continent into two separate states namely India and Pakistan, being Hindu majority and Muslim majority states respectively. Mountbatten flew to Karachi to transfer of Power to the newly created state of Pakistan on 14 the August 1947. Quaid-e- Azzam Muhammad Ali Jinnah was sworn in the first Governor General of Pakistan. Liaquat Ali Khan took over as the first Prime Minister. Pakistan was the first ever state that was built on the basis of religion.

History of Israel:

Before creation of Israel, it was under the control of Britain. British control lasted from 1923 to 1948. During this period the authorities were challenged by the demands from Zionists for Jewish self-Government and a growing Arab Nationalist Movement rejecting this Jewish presence. On November 29, 1947, the UN General Assembly voted on the partition plan. When the UN gave vote for partition, the Mandate on November 29, 1947, Palestine Arab with the help of Arab States, they launched attacks against Israel to seize the entire mandate. On May 14, 1948 Israel declared independence.ⁱ

Economic Development of Pakistan and Israel:

At the time of Partition, the new government lacked the personnel, institutions, and resources to play a large role in developing the economy. To rise from such a state surely is a great task, especially when one's borders are also insecure.ⁱⁱ The disruptions caused by partition, the interruption of trade with India, the strict control of imports, and the overvalued exchange rate necessitated immediate action on the part of the government. Government policies afforded liberal incentives to industrialization, while public development of the infrastructure complemented private investment.ⁱⁱⁱ Some public manufacturing plants were established by government holding companies.^{iv} Manufacturing proved highly profitable, attracting increasing private investments and reinvestment of profits.^v Except for large government investments in the Indus irrigation system, agriculture was left largely alone in the 1950s. The broad outline of government policy in the 1950s involved squeezing the agriculture and workers to finance industrial development. In 1955, there was a survey held which tried to give the false impression of full employment in the agriculture sector. However, this proved wrong when in 1965 a survey was held and it was found that the economy of Pakistan was most stagnant in the region and a 50% ratio of underemployed labor to the total working force could be taken as nearer to reality.^{vi} In all the five-year plan starting from 1955, policies were included at the reduction of unemployment, however due to inadequate efforts on the part of the government most of them proved decreased.^{vii}

In 1971 Pakistan lost its east wing which became Bangladesh. It greatly affected economy because East Pakistan was the major producer of Jute.^{viii} This occurred mainly because of war with India and also because Pakistan lost revenue which it used to earn from Bangladesh. Then Bhutto Prime Minister of Pakistan devalued the Rupee by 131% which boasted our exports by 153%. introduced several reforms and public development projects because of which Pakistan was able to achieve the average growth rate of 7.5 till 1974.^{ix} In 1975, the height of Bhutto's nationalization program, private sector investment was only 15% of the total. Cotton crop was also destroyed and there were several floods during his last years of rule. 1976 saw Pakistan's worst floods, devastating large areas of cultivated land. All these factors caused Pakistan's GDP to fall significantly and from 1974-1977, the average GDP was just 3.6%.^x

Zia-ul-Haq revived the confidence in Private Sector to invest in the country again.^{xi} The process of privatization was carried out gradually. The inflow of foreign aid from US and other countries increased because of Pakistan's role in war against the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics. This increased the income of local people and the domestic demand of goods and services increased. This aid also helped Zia regime to finance in the industrial sector. This all caused Pakistan's GDP to grow by average 6.5% during 1980-88 and at that time it was only exceeded by that of Korea, China and Hong Kong.^{xii}

During the time of General Pervez Musharraf, the economy grew at an average rate of 6.3 percent a year. After Pakistan joined in the war against terror it received foreign aid of billions of dollars.^{xiii} Heavy development projects were launched and boost the growth rate. 7 licenses were sold to cellular companies at a very high cost and many state-owned companies were privatized. These firms started to perform well and their productivity increased.^{xiv} Tax collection increased by 18 percent during July-April 2007 and exports increased by 18.3 percent and imports up by 8.9 percent.^{xv} However, only the Services sector grew significantly and not the manufacturing sector. No major industries were set up and in 2008 when there was a worldwide recession, Pakistan's economy suffered heavily.^{xvi}

Unemployment is one of the major problems of Pakistan. It is the root cause of several other problems and is a result of a number of problems.^{xvii} High unemployment results in wastage of resources and depression of income.^{xviii} And most certainly it also effects the social and emotional life of a person.

Before the 1970s, Pakistan linked its currency, rupee, to the Pound Sterling. With the economic influence of the USA getting more apparent, in 1971, Pakistan linked rupee to the U.S. Dollar. In 1972 Bhutto devalued Pakistani rupee by 131%.^{xix} The exchange rate at that time was \$1= PKR 11.^{xx} This act significantly increased our export revenue. Despite the loss of East Pakistan's exportable produce, West Pakistan doubled its foreign exchange earnings.^{xxi} However, in 1973, OPEC increased the price of oil and Pakistan had to pay higher price to import oil. During that year there was a worldwide recession and the demand for goods and services decreased throughout the world which also caused Pakistan's export to decline. All these factors greatly damaged Pakistan's economy.

From 1999-2007 during Musharraf's rule, the exchange rate remained stable at \$1=PKR 60. The reason for this was high amount of foreign air and remittances inflow in Pakistan.^{xxii} In 2008 due to sky rocketing rates of oil and unstable political and security conditions, Pakistan felt short of its foreign reserves and the price of \$1 reached all-time high to PKR 86.7.

In the early half century Israel was a poor new state heavily indebted in the World. Israel can be described as rapidly growing country because of their successful industrialization. In 1980s, due to economically overburdened the growth and developments was stopped in Israel. After a decade, Washington consensus report showed that Israel is successful adaption to globalization and technological change. In 1990's, Israel economy enjoyed a wave of growth to the Asian tiger economics and Israel's real per capita gross domestic product grew by a remarkable four percent per annum. Furthermore, the modern Jewish settlement in Palestine, geopolitics and capital inflows have boost the Israel's economy.

This situation becomes remarkable. The economy was stable and government subsidized the business and house items. In 1985, the hyperinflation has been stopped due to stabilization. The private sectors have experienced globalization through foreign trade.

However, in 1990's Israel plays a vital role in political economy. They attract people and capital from outside to managing the internal conflicts. The Israel's multiple roles in external relations like; military, manpower and fund-raising policy with the legitimated activism in economic affairs.

Today's, the Global Competitive Report of 2016- 2017 ranked Israel as having the second most innovative economy in the World.

Efforts by Israel to establish relations with Pakistan and wars between Israel and Arab world:

- In 1947, Israel's first Prime minister David Ben-Gurion's telegram to establish diplomatic relations with Pakistan to Jinnah but no particular response.^{xxiii}
- 1948- The independent country of Israel was declared. The first Prime Minister of Israel was David Ben-Gurion. Golda Meir.
- 1948- Israel was attacked by a coalition of Arab countries including Egypt, Jordan, Iraq, Syria and Lebanon in the first Arab-Israeli war. The Israelis won the war.
- 1949-the first Knesset (Israeli assembly) is held. Israel becomes a member of the United Nations.
- Later in 1950, Pakistan's refusal passage permission the Jewish transition from India to Israel asked by Israel then left by Iran.
- In 1952, Sir Zafar Ullah Khan, Fame Star's policies toward Israel (the unity of Arab states results to build strategic ties with the Arab states).
- 1956-the sues crisis occurs when Egypt takes control of the sues canal.
- In 1960, football match against each other, (AFC Asian Cups).

- The Pakistan Air Force's participation in the 1967 Six-Days War. (between Israel and a group of Arab countries).
- In the 1973 Yom Kippur War.(Egypt and Syria attack on Israel on the Jewish holy day of Yom Kippur, Israel pushed back the Egyptian army).
- After, Pakistan's and the PLO's agreement for training PLO officers in Pakistani military institutions.
- 1979- Israel signed a peace treaty with Egypt at Camp David in the United States.
- 1980- The shekel becomes the official currency of Israel replacing the Israeli lira.
- In 1981, attack on Iraq's Osiris nuclear reactors.
- 1982 Lebanon War, Pakistani volunteers served in the PLO and 50 were taken prisoner during the Siege of Beirut.^{xxiv}
- In the 1980's a similar plan to attack Pakistan's Kahutta Research facility using Indian airfields that was failed. Pakistan got alerted and took preventive measures.
- 1991- The Gulf war occurred. Israel was hit by Scud missiles from Iraq.
- In 1993, Benazir Bhutto along with her then DG of Military Operation's Pervez Musharraf had intensified the ISI's liaison with Mossad. (Mossad is the national intelligence agency of Israel).
- 1998 allegation's reply, conservative P.M.N. Sharif sent a secret courier to Israel counterpart Benjamin Netanyahu (not transfer our nuclear technology to Iran to aid in their nuclear program, even though Iran's foreign minister had paid a visit).
- In 2003, President Pervez Musharraf raised the issue of possible diplomatic relations with the Israel.
- In 2005, both countries foreign ministers talk for the first time.
- Musharraf said that Pakistan will not recognize the state of Israel until an independent Palestinian state is established, although, according to Musharraf, Pakistan will eventually recognize Israel.^{xxv}
- In 2009- Benjamin Netanyahu is elected prime minister.
- In 2010, Pakistan's embassy in Istanbul passing info i.e. terror group to Israel according to WikiLeaks. (Both, considered as enemies).
- In 2011, Israel, British military technology to Pakistan. (electronic warfare systems and aircraft parts)
- Israel denied the report and Pakistan called the revelations "misleading."^{xxvi}
- In 2015, an Israeli scientist, Rajni Suleiman attended a scientific conference sponsored by the P. Academy. Sci's held in Lahore, Pakistan.
- On Thursday, October 1, 2015, Israeli Prime Minister Netanyahu cancelled dining in at Serafina (N.Y).
- As the P. M. of Pakistan Mian Muhammad Nawaz Sharif too was dining in at the same time due to his harsh opinion over "Israel's naked brutality in Palestine"^{xxvii}
- During the 2002, Israeli tennis player Amir Hadid teamed up with Pakistani tennis player Aisam-ul-Haq Qureshi. (headline news).
- Dan Kiesel, an Israeli-born German, served as the Pakistan cricket team's trainer and physiotherapist and lived in Lahore.
- Former Foreign Minister of Pakistan Khurshid Kasuri supported ties between Pakistan and Israel.

Israel and the Middle Eastern Insight:

Since gaining independence in 1948, and latterly joining the United Nations in 1949, Israel has been known to participate in many conflicts with various countries. Israel is perhaps the only country in the world that is under never ending threat ever since its creation. It is located in the midst of Arab countries that are still trying to reconcile with the creation of the country. Israel has fought many wars with these countries and continues to face aggression and acts of terrorism and sabotage on daily basis. Since always Israel had an intrinsically contradictory attitude in terms of its relationship with Middle Eastern countries. Middle East can be doubtlessly considered as a region that lacks stability.

This aggressive attitude of Israel has given rise to “Arab – Israel Conflict”, in particular warlike conflict with Palestine. Since 1970’s this region was dominated by the Turkish and Ottoman Empire. But after the Islamic Revolution in 1979, Iran and latterly Turkey have emerged as the strongest Muslim political powers in the Middle East and have sustained this influence in the early years of the 21st Century. The arrival of these two countries have had intense impact on the region’s politics. By time Turkey could not maintain the frequency of dominance over the region. Iran steered the leadership and its revolutionary image in the region and changed the views of several middle eastern countries towards region’s politics.

- *Iran* being a forerunner for nuclear technology and an active missile development program, Israel feels seriously threatened by Iran. The anti US sentiment of Iran and support of the Palestinian cause adds on to Israel’s anxiety. A nuclear capable Iran would be of serious threat to Israel. In the past as well, Iran has maintained connections with Hamas and Hezbollah in Beirut and reportedly assisted these organizations to target Israel.
- *Although Saudi Arabia* and Israel do not share any mutual official relations but both countries share interest in some common factors that are, they have a firm opposition to Iran’s nuclear program, Iran’s quest for Regional hegemony in Middle East, concerns with rise of Jihadist in regional politics. However, Saudi Arabia has a modern army with some of the latest fighters and continues to grow. The anti US and Israel sentiment of opposition groups in the Kingdom are of concern to Israel. Any regime change in the Saudi Arabia will be critical to the Israelis.
- Israel and **Egypt** have common interest in the Sinai Peninsula and Gaza strip (part of Palestine) (borders with Egypt on the south west & with Israel on the east and north). Egypt shares diplomatic relations with Israel and also has dependency on Israel for Natural Gas and Water supply.
- The crisis in **Syria** initially emerged as protest against the government of Bashar al Assad, further eruption caused the protestors to take up arms not just for their self-defense, but to exile the government forces from their local towns, this situation has further on taken a turn as conflict between Sunni and Shia community of the country. Despite Palestine another major dilemma Israel is going through is “how to deal with Syrian Crisis”. The factors that greatly influence this crisis for Israel are that Syria being a neighboring state, a dreadful military foe, a partner in inconsistent peace negotiations, this all led to an extensive & horrifically destructive civil war which triggered a proxy war scenario between the regional and international rivals. In such crisis, it may would have been possible that many small states emerge from the breakup of this larger state of Syria which would also result in disposition of much advanced weapon system. Israel had a double minded opinion about Syria, on

one side Israel believes that it would have been preferable if Bashar al Asaad remains in power in Syria instead jihadist taking over the regime. On the other side Israel thinks that Bashar al Asaad's survival may lead to the coalition of Iran-Syria-Hezbollah. In the wake of recent happenings, after defeat of ISIS in Syria, problems for Israel have further compounded as Russia and Iran have cashed upon the support of present Syrian Government in a better way than any influence which could have been exercised by Israel. Israel has always kept a careful response towards Syrian crisis, Syria remains Israel's principal immediate military threat. The country continues to expand its arsenal of weapons. It has the capability to manufacture several hundred tons of chemical warfare agents per year and is reportedly building its own ballistic missiles from imported technology with help of Korea and Russia mainly. Syria has more troops and tanks, and nearly as many aircraft as Israel.

- Israel and **Jordon** have maintained an unstated but effective security cooperation. Jordon is confident that it can count on Israel providing safety to her in case of a major crisis emerging from any Islamic state or Syria. Jordon depends on Israel for Natural Gas and Water supply. In case of Palestinian animosity of Israel, Jordon seems to be supporting Palestine by pressurizing Israel to accept Palestine statehood. At present no threat emanates to Israel from Jordan especially after the peace accord in 1994. Military relations between both the countries are improving. However, being an Arab country, Israel still eyes Jordan with doubt. Continuous expansion of Jordanian Army and Defense deals with US to provide Jordan with additional F-16 fighters as well as missiles is a matter of concern to Israel.
- Israel and **Lebanon** have never been in relationship as far as economic, diplomatic military dynamics are concerned. Lebanon has negative opinions about Israel and strongly prohibits Israeli passport to enter Lebanon territory. The major factors inflicting Lebanon and Israel relationship are the Natural Gas Dispute, Border incidents, Lebanon War.

Can Pakistan and Israel Become Allies?

It is hard to imagine bilateral relationships between Israel, a Jewish state, and any Muslim nation & in the same way Pakistan is not exceptional. Since independence of both countries, several efforts have been made to develop relationship. Considering international dynamics within Muslim countries and world affairs, whenever talks about Israel and Pakistan relationship take place than the concept of crusaders emerges. Although they are Jewish but they are backed by Christians, and whenever Christians help Jews it is always in animosity with Muslims and to effect Muslims destructively. Otherwise as well, Jewish lobby dominates America and Americans are the Super Power, in this concept America has to support Israel in any way possible. As far as Pakistan's sentimental relations, religious relations and compromising relationship with Muslim countries is concerned, it is not possible that Pakistan and Israel makeup long-term relationships. From the perspective of the nation of Pakistan that is common people of Pakistan, there are certain religious sentiments among the people that, on the name of Islam, they are ready to shed blood of each other without even giving a second thought, therefore it is very difficult to mould the thinking of our own people to make them understand that we only want prosperous and beneficial relations with Israel. At this point of time it is also important that the world politics and Pakistan's own relationships with other countries in the world also matter greatly in terms of forwarding a fact. In present scenario it is very difficult to extend any hands of friendship with Israel, especially after the recent

happening, in which US President Donald Trump declared Jerusalem as accepted capital of Israel, and decision to make a consulate in Israel. However, as nowadays there are many protests happening all around the world by Muslim countries as well as some European countries which is indirectly an effort to pressurize America to take her decision back, probably in the UN's forum. This may not be as easy as it seems because the America's dominate the UN, rather UN should dominate America. But if America is pressurized to an extent that it becomes nearly difficult to stand on the decision as recently after defeat in Syria war, the ISIS and Daish defeat which was presumably backed by America, but Russian have succeeded there, so comparatively US is in pressure, even in Afghanistan US is not able to get the gains it had aimed for, and any future involvement of Russia in Afghanistan is also a matter of concern for America as well. At this point of time America does not want to bitter its relations with Pakistan because if they cause any harm to Pakistan, Russia would definitely get involved, as Pakistan is important for Russia from CPEC's point of view. America knows that due to the highly invested and economically enriched project of CPEC, Pakistan has got Russia and China's full support.

In future perspective if we consider that this overall scenario might change, and situation is normalized in Israel and with its surrounding countries than covertly Pakistan can initiate certain steps mainly trade oriented, weapons support and as a goodwill gesture, but as far as full fledged relationship (such as friendly relations) is concerned it is not possible from point of view of both countries dynamics which includes the religion foremost, As per a Quranic verse of Surah -e- Maida, it is narrated: "O ye who believe! Take not the Jews and the Christians for your friends and protectors; They are but friends and protectors to each other. And he amongst you who turns to them (for friendship) is of them. Verily God guided not a people unjust."^{xxviii} And this concept is taken sacredly by every Muslim to some extent, because the religious values hold great importance than material values, as religion is the basis. So, Pakistan can only keep a moderate relationship as the Goodwill gesture for benefits, but there can never be a trustworthy and reliable relationship between both countries, rather a diplomatic relation for a win-win situation maybe kept. Instead a win loss relation in any context as it would lead to hostile results. Israel and Pakistan, presently do not have any ties because they think of themselves as the embodiment of ideology. Nonetheless, one is free to visualize what would be the political scenario if there existed a relationship between Israel and Pakistan. According to Kumar swami (2000), ties between countries are possible, while matching their ideologies can be difficult. On this basis, it is safe to argue that even if Israel and Pakistan have different ideologies, their attempts to bolster relations can be fruitful resulting in strengthened bilateral ties. However, the question that remains is what the political situation would be.

Palestine as a Road Block:

Palestinians, the Arab population, hailing from the land currently controlled by Israel. There have been constant efforts to end the turmoil, but as a matter of fact, Palestine remains a roadblock to a peaceful roadmap. Since Israel became an independent state in 1948, she has continuously experienced assassinations, bombings, kidnappings, death threats, and military strikes. She has for long struggled for peace, but her efforts continue to be plagued by turmoil and violence. Reportedly, Palestine is the major stumbling block to peace for various reasons. Unless Palestine authorities take action and call for an immediate and unconditional ceasefire to all acts of incitement, violence, and terrorism against Israelis, Israel will not withdraw from Palestinian towns. For peace to prevail, both sides and all the parties within them must set aside all doubts, personal grudges, fears, and thoughts of revenge. Palestine ought to arrest, disrupt, and restrain its individuals and groups from planning and executing violent attacks against Israel. Continued resistance of the occupation by Palestine particularly Hamas has been a pain

in the neck for Israel. With Hamas now in the Government and their refusal to recognize Israel is a matter of grave concern. Threat of terrorist attacks in Israel is a reality, and everyday threat. Palestine are fighting a battle of justice for their right, and as being a Muslim state, they expect other Muslim states to support them. Palestine would always expect sympathy from Pakistan as it is one of the powerful Muslim country.

Israel's Relations with India and its impact on Pakistan:

India and Israel are celebrating their 25th year of diplomatic relations. Interesting historical fact is that India recognized Israel in 1950 but established its relation in 1992. This is because India didn't want to harm its relations with Arabs and wanted to have Muslims majority in the country to be supportive of the foreign policy. The relationship turned out to be extremely beneficial for India, having weaponry support in Kargil war against Pakistan by Israel was a crucial factor in the relationship.

Military Collaboration:

In January 2012, India and Israel signed a pact on transfer of sentenced prisoners. In 2014 India and Israel signed intelligence sharing agreement to fight Islamic extremist. In November 2014, Indian-Israeli Barak 8 air and naval defense missile system took place. Since the new government after 2014 elections Israel exported 662\$ million worth Israeli weapons. India uses Israeli-made unmanned drones for surveillance and military purposes. Indian firm Reliance defense and Israeli firm Rafael Advance defense Systems have jointly agreed on March, 2016 to produce air-to-air missiles and weaponry. Indian navy launched Israeli-developed Integrated Under-Water Harbor Defense and Surveillance System (IUHDSS), in February 2017. The Indian military has deployed an Israeli-developed comprehensive integrated border management system (CIBMS) along its border with Pakistan in August 2017 in order to advance surveillance technology.^{xxix}

Other Developments:

India and Israel started 50\$ million shared agriculture funds on dairy, farming, micro-irrigation and water technologies. India and Israel have also been working collaboratively on government level to confront waste water issues. They have developed newest technologies for the waste water treatment. In the last few years the relations have developed stronger and tourism from both countries has also been promoted. Both governments have been coordinating since 2014 elections followed by the official visits of state dignitaries from both sides with respect to the defense, technology, education, agriculture, tourism and foreign policy.

Indian-Israel relations and Pakistan:

Israel has helped India greatly in the wars of 1965, 1971 and 1999, against Pakistan. Pakistan is one of those Muslim countries that are totally against the ideology of Israel on the basis of Pakistan's own ideology. This is harmful for Pakistan and in the favor of Indian enmity towards Pakistan. But if the idea of talking to Israel and recognizing it is floated on any forum in Pakistan, the consequences can be devastating within Pakistan and might not be controllable. So, in a nutshell this whole situation of Israel is a big & complex challenge to our foreign policy and hence needs to be handled smartly.

Islamic Perspective for Not Recognizing Israel:

one of the main factors of not being friends with Israel is our Islamic perspective. We believe that Islam restrains us to do so. Quran says^{xxx}

“O you who believe, do not take [certain] Jews and Christians as allies; these are allies of one another. Those among you who ally themselves with these belong with them. God does not guide the transgressors.”

And what we conclude by this verse is that Jews and Christians cannot be our friends. It would not be right for us to only look at a particular perspective. Because we know that every verse of Quran was revealed in different contexts. Now let's have a look on different verses of Quran. on another place Quran says: ^{xxxi}

“God does not enjoin you from befriending those who do not fight you because of religion, and do not evict you from your homes. You may befriend them and be equitable towards them. God loves the equitable.”

“God enjoins you only from befriending those who fight you because of religion, evict you from your homes, and band together with others to banish you. You shall not befriend them. Those who befriend them are the transgressors.”

That totally shows that Muslims cannot be friends with those who fight with them because of religion and any kind conflict between the believers and non-believers. So, this would not be right if we say that we cannot be friends with all the Jews, until they fight. On the other hand, verses like these can also be found:

“Among the followers of Moses there are those who guide in accordance with the truth, and the truth renders them righteous.”^{xxxii}

“Surely, those who believe, those who are Jewish, the Christians, and the converts; anyone who (1) believes in God, and (2) believes in the Last Day, and (3) leads a righteous life, will receive their recompense from their Lord. They have nothing to fear, nor will they grieve.”^{xxxiii}

“They are not all the same; among the followers of the scripture, there are those who are righteous. They recite God's revelations through the night, and they fall prostrate.”^{xxxiv}

“Surely, some followers of the previous scriptures do believe in God, and in what was revealed to you, and in what was revealed to them. They reverence God, and they never trade away God's revelations for a cheap price. These will receive their recompense from their Lord. God is the most efficient in reckoning.”^{xxxv}

The one who believe in GOD and believe in the Last Day, they support righteousness and forbid evil, and they do righteous works. They are the righteous. According to these verses, we can say Jews are also righteous and now question arises if they are righteous why we Muslim hate Jews and do not recognize their country?

Charter of medina can also be referred where Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) gave equal rights to the Jews of medina. What we can conclude from all of this is that we can be friends with Jews but can never rely or trust them. We should be friends with them for the world peace.

Conclusion:

Pakistan can be benefited in various ways if the bilateral relations are established between Pakistan and Israel. But according to many reasons it is very difficult to say if Pakistan is ready to do so or not. As we have seen already, the reactive approach Pakistanis adopted when Donald Trump gave decision in favor of **Israel**. We People of Pakistan do not want to establish any kind of relations with Israel. Israel's relations with India can harm Pakistan, because they have

become very good friends. Israel is neither our friend nor our foe, if proper steps are taken towards Israel for better relations, Israel can be a good business partner.

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between Israel and Pakistan. According to Kumar swami (2000), ties between countries are possible, while matching their ideologies can be difficult. On this basis, it is safe to argue that even if Israel and Pakistan have different ideologies, their attempts to bolster relations can be fruitful resulting in strengthened bilateral ties. However, the question that remains is what the political situation would be.

Recommendations:

On the basis of analysis, following is recommended:

- The relationship between Israel and Pakistan would be one in which both countries act as mediators. Cooperating on political and diplomatic levels, Pakistan would likely become a mediator between Israel and Palestine, while Israel would become a mediator between Pakistan and India with regard to the Indian-Pakistan dispute over Kashmir.
- Besides, if Israel and Pakistan had good relations, Pakistan would benefit from Israel's strong lobbying powers in the world to improve her image in the eyes of the international community. Moreover, if Israel and Pakistan were on good terms, Pakistan can leverage on Israel's lobbying powers to foster healthy relationships with other countries of the world. No major countries support Pakistan apart from Saudi Arabia and China.
- In case there is cooperation b/w Israel and Pakistan, the two could succeed in dealing with militant extremism, which is a common challenge. A peaceful and fruitful cooperation can be in the field of agriculture (Kumar Swamy, 2000). Pakistan can gain considerably from Israel's unmatched expertise in taming the desert for agricultural purposes. Pakistan has vast desert lands that remain uncultivated.
- Pakistan can covertly initiate certain steps mainly trade oriented, weapons support and as a goodwill gesture can be developed.
- We cannot strain our relations with Israel because in contrary if India's relations with Israel become stronger, especially in terms of arms deal, as this would be highly alarming situation for Pakistan. As Longtime back in the 90's when Pakistan was testing the nuclear experiments, Israel has been planning coalition with India to attack Khan Research Laboratories atchara. Therefore, Pakistan has to avoid every such situation that would ignite Israel to take militant steps towards Pakistan.

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